

RPE-guided training: impact on perceptual responses in adults with spinal cord injury

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Abstract The aim of this study was to investigate the impact of training with or without RPE-guidance on the peripheral (RPE_P) and central (RPE_C) RPE responses to moderate-vigorous exercise in adults with SCI. Nineteen participants (41 ± 11 years) with chronic SCI were randomly assigned to either RPE-guided (n = 11; EXP) or active control (n = 8; CON) groups. EXP performed 16 weeks of supervised aerobic training for 20 mins, twice weekly, at 3-6 using the CR-10 RPE scale. CON used the same exercise equipment but received no advice as to their exercise training regime. Participants completed a graded exercise test (GXT) using an arm crank ergometer pre and post-training to determine peak oxygen uptake ($\dot{V}O_{2peak}$). Of interest, were the post-training RPE_P and RPE_C, which were recorded each minute throughout the GXT. The training did not lead to an improvement in $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ in EXP or CON. Post-training, at 50% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ there was no significant difference between RPE_P and RPE_C (1.5 ± 0.9 vs 1.2 ± 0.9 , $P = 0.12$), or EXP and CON (1.5 ± 0.9 v. 1.2 ± 0.9 , $P = 0.39$); at 70% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ RPE_P was significantly higher than RPE_C (3.7 ± 1.2 vs 3.0 ± 1.3 , $P = 0.01$, $ES = 0.61$), however there was no difference between EXP and CON (3.5 ± 1.5 vs 3.2 ± 1.0 , $P = 0.70$). Training with or without RPE-guidance for 16 weeks had no effect on post-training aerobic capacity or differentiated RPE response to moderate-vigorous exercise in adults with SCI. These data challenge whether familiarisation or anchoring of RPE is necessary for effective use of RPE to regulate exercise intensity in this SCI population, but support greater emphasis being placed on RPE_P.

Keywords perceived exertion, familiarisation, peripheral, central

Introduction

For adults with spinal cord injury (SCI), the use of ratings of perceived exertion (RPE) offers a feasible and cost-effective tool for monitoring exercise intensity during a training program. Furthermore using differentiated measures of peripheral (RPE_P) and central (RPE_C) RPE may be more appropriate than an overall value (van der Scheer, Hutchinson et al. 2018). Prior to using RPE for prescribing exercise intensity it is recommended to conduct a familiarisation trial to improve validity (Pageaux 2016), however has never been investigated in participants with SCI. The aim of the present study was to investigate a period of prolonged familiarisation with RPE, via RPE-guided exercise training, on the perceptual response to moderate-vigorous exercise in adults with SCI.

Methods

Participants

Nineteen participants with chronic SCI were recruited and randomly allocated to either RPE-based exercise (EXP; $n = 11$; 40.9 ± 10.7 years; 88.3 ± 17.8 kg; C3-T11) or active control (CON; $n = 8$; 42.1 ± 12.9 years; 79.1 ± 15.8 kg; C4-T11) group.

Exercise testing

All participants completed a graded exercise test (GXT) using an arm crank ergometer pre and post the training intervention. The GXT started at 0-15 W and was increased by 5-10 W·min⁻¹ until the participants reached volitional exhaustion. Gas exchange and ventilatory variables were collected using Moxus Metabolic System (AEI Technologies, Pittsburgh, PA, USA). In the final 10 s of each minute, RPE_P and RPE_C were recorded using the CR-10. Participants were instructed to focus on the degree of physical strain in the exercising musculature (RPE_P) and cardiorespiratory systems (RPE_C).

Exercise intervention

All participants underwent a 16-week exercise training intervention. Participants in the EXP group completed a supervised, progressive exercise program that consisted of 20 min of RPE-guided aerobic exercise, twice weekly, at 3-6 on the CR-10. Participants were instructed to adjust the workload accordingly throughout training sessions in order to maintain the required RPE. The CON group had access to the same exercise equipment as the EXP group, but received no guidance on the type, amount or intensity of exercise training to perform.

Statistics

Differences in the post-training between-group peak exercise responses were assessed using independent t-tests. For the post-testing timepoint RPE_P and RPE_C were fit against % $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ using a quadratic function, with values corresponding to 50 and 70% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ calculated. To compare the post-training differentiated RPE responses between groups at 50 and 70% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, 2 x 2 mixed measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used; the between-measures factor being group (EXP vs CON), and the within-measure factor being type of RPE (RPE_P vs RPE_C).

Results

There was no significant difference in the pre and post $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ for EXP (18.6 ± 6.2 vs 19.8 ± 7.3 ml·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹) or CON (18.7 ± 6.0 vs 18.3 ± 7.3 ml·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹). Regarding the perceptual responses, at 50% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ there was no main effect of group (EXP: 1.5 ± 0.9 vs CON: 1.2 ± 0.9 ; $P = 0.39$; ES = 0.37) or type of RPE (RPE_P: 1.5 ± 0.9 vs RPE_C: 1.2 ± 0.9 ; $P = 0.12$; ES = 0.42), and no RPE type by training group interaction ($P = 0.35$) (Figure 1). At 70% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ there was a main effect of type of RPE with a moderate ES (RPE_P: 3.7 ± 1.2 vs RPE_C: 3.0 ± 1.3 ; $P = 0.01$; ES = 0.61). There was, however, no main effect of group (EXP: 3.5 ± 1.5 vs CON: 3.2 ± 1.0 ; $P = 0.70$; ES = 0.17), or RPE type by training group interaction ($P = 0.87$).

Figure 1. RPE_P and RPE_C responses at 50 and 70% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$ during incremental arm crank ergometry, post 16-weeks training for RPE-guided (EXP) and active control (CON) groups. EXP_P: RPE_P for the EXP group; CON_P: RPE_P for the CON group; EXP_C: RPE_C for the EXP group; CON_C: RPE_C for the CON group. *: RPE_P greater than RPE_C at 70% $\dot{V}O_{2peak}$, $P < 0.05$.

Conclusion

Training with, or without, RPE-guidance for 16-weeks had no effect on the differentiated RPE responses to moderate-vigorous exercise in adults with SCI. These data challenge whether familiarisation with RPE is necessary for the effective use of differentiated RPE in regulating exercise intensity in the SCI population. However, given the difference between RPE_P and RPE_C at higher intensities, attention must be paid to how differentiated RPE is implemented as a tool for regulating exercise intensity in adults with SCI.

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